

ISic2984

I.Sicily inscription 2984

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula ansata

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.05 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Enna

Place of origin (modern)

Enna

Provenance

'in localita Porto Salvo, non lungi dalla torre di Federico II' during
military works Nov. 1942

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Enna, Museo Archeologico
Varisano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175842

EDR 073827

EDCS 13900574

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 242 dr
Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia
Classica.* 17: 183-210. At 189 tav.65.2

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